

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF UNITIZED ORTHOTROPIC RECESSED STRUCTURE UNDER COMBINED AXIAL AND TRANSVERSE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The rapidly expanding applications of advanced composites have provided much optimism for the future of aerospace technology. Materials and processing advances, particularly with graphite fiber /epoxy matrix (Gr/Ep) materials, have been instrumental in the growth of the technology. Much more recent advances have been in the area of unitized (cocured) construction. Structural analysis of such structure, Gr/Ep unitized construction, with recess is the subject of this paper.

INTRODUCTION

Shown in Figure 1 is an example of a basic unit structure representing a discontinuity in the outer mold line silhouette (wetted surface). The need for the discontinuity could be a number of things such as a door joggle, an antenna mounting, a fairing recess, an edge extension, etc. Conventionally, the substructure is made of an isotropic material such as an aluminum wrought alloy (Al-Zn-Mg-Cu-Zr) developed to

have a combination of high strength, high resistance to stress-corrosion cracking, and good fracture toughness, particularly in thick sections. The skin is made from an orthotropic material such as a Gr/Ep unidirectional-ply multidirectional laminate. The skin is mechanically fastened to the substructure using titanium (preferred) and/or insulated high-strength steel fasteners. Proper design of attachments and joints is essential to insure that imposed loads do not contribute to premature failure due to stress concentrations occurring at such sites. At the same time, unnecessary stress concentrations resulting from unduly conservative design must be avoided if smooth load transitioning is desired

Figure 1. Before unitized design.

Shown in Figure 2 is an example of a basic unit structure representing a transition in the outer mold line silhouette (wetted surface). The need for the transition is the same as for the discontinuity previously discussed. Both the substructure and the skin are made of orthotropic material such as Gr/Ep unidirectional-ply multidirectional laminate. The substructure is cocured to the skin (no adhesive) to produce a unitized construction. The result is a smoother transition in loading, producing a more reliable structure.

Figure 2. After unitized design.

DISCUSSIONS

The transition or recessed structure (Figure 2) is schematically represented in Figure 3a. The schematic is analogous to a beam end supports (simply supported) under axial compression and transverse center load as shown in Figure 3b.¹

Figure 3. The specific structural analysis addressed is for kick-load stresses at the recess (orthotropic recessed plate under combined axial & transverse load).

The general equations, as well as boundary values and selected maximum values, for the case of axial compressive loading plus transverse loading for a beam simply supported at both ends follows (In general, axial tension is a less critical condition because deflections, slopes and moments from transverse loading are usually reduced by axial tensile loading.):

$$M_{\max} (@ x = L/2) = 1/2[W j \tan(U/2)] \quad (1)$$

where

$$M_{\max} = \text{maximum moment at } x = L/2 \text{ (in-lb/in or N-m/m)}$$

$$L = \text{length of beam (in or m)} \quad (2)$$

$$W = \text{transverse loading} = 4m/L \text{ (lb/in or N/m)} \quad (2)$$

$$m = e (\Sigma N)_{x \max} \text{ (lb or N)} \quad (3)$$

$$e = \text{eccentricity (in or m)}$$

$$(\Sigma N)_{x \max} = \text{maximum spanwise running load in panel for external load condition (lb/in or N/m)}$$

$$j = [EI/P]^{1/2} \text{ (in or m)} \quad (4)$$

$$E = \text{modulus of elasticity (psi or Pa)}$$

$$I = \text{moment of inertia of cross section about horizontal central axis (in}^4 \text{ or m}^4 \text{)}$$

$$P = \text{axial load (lb or N)}$$

$$U = L/j (X 360^\circ / 2\pi \text{ radians} = \text{degrees}) \quad (5)$$

From elementary theory, we know that rigidity of an isotropic (homogeneous) beam is:

$$\text{Rigidity} = EI = M/k_1 \quad (6)$$

where

$$k_1 = \text{the resulting curvature along the 1-axis.}$$

From the moment-curvature relation of symmetric laminates in terms of compliance², we also know that under simple bending of M relative to the 1-axis only, the resulting curvature along the 1-axis is:

$$k_1 = d_{11} M/b = M/bD_{11} \quad (7)$$

where

$$d_{11} = \text{flexural compliance of multidirectional symmetric laminate and the inverse of } D_{11} \text{ (in}^2 \text{/lb-in}^2 \text{ or m}^2 \text{/N-m}^2 \text{)}$$

$$D_{11} = \text{flexural modulus of multidirectional symmetric laminate (lb-in}^2 \text{/in}^2 \text{ or N-m}^2 \text{/m}^2 \text{)}$$

$$b = \text{finite width of beam or plate (in or m)}$$

By combining the two relationships (equations (6) and (7)), we have:

$$EI = bD_{11} \quad (8)$$

Substituting $b(\Sigma N_x)_{\max}$ for P , $j = [EI/P]^{1/2}$ becomes

$$j = [(bD_{11}) / (b(\Sigma N_x)_{\max})]^{1/2} = [D_{11} / (\Sigma N_x)_{\max}]^{1/2} \text{ (in or m)} \quad (9)$$

where

$$D_{11} = 2 \Sigma G_{11} t x^2 \text{ about center line (lb-in}^2/\text{in or N-m}^2/\text{m)} \quad (10)$$

$$G_{11} = \bar{Q}_{11} \text{ (msi or GPa)}$$

$$= Q_{11} \cos^4 \theta + Q_{22} \sin^4 \theta + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66}) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta \quad (11)$$

$$Q_{11} = E_L / (1 - \nu_{LT} \nu_{TL}) \text{ (msi or GPa)} \quad (12)$$

$$Q_{22} = E_T / (1 - \nu_{LT} \nu_{TL}) \text{ (msi or GPa)} \quad (13)$$

$$Q_{12} = \nu_{21} Q_{11} \text{ (msi or GPa)} \quad (14)$$

$$\nu_{21} = \nu_{TL} = \nu_{LT} E_T / E_L \quad (15)$$

$$Q_{66} = G_{LT} \text{ (msi or GPa)} \quad (16)$$

An example of D_{11} applied to a laminate is presented in Figure 4 and Table 1.

Figure 4. Example of multidirectional symmetric laminate (Gr/Ep 25% 0°, 50% ± 45°, 25% 90°).

Table 1. Calculation of flexural modulus of multidirectional symmetric laminate shown in Figure 4.

θ	$G_{11} =$
45°	$Q_{11} (0.25) + Q_{22} (0.25) + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66}) (0.5)(0.5)$
90°	Q_{22}
0°	Q_{11}

n	θ	G_{11}	t	x	$G_{11} t x^2$
		(GPa)	(m)	(m)	(N-m ² /m)
1	± 45	43.154688	0.0002642	0.0003962	1.7897 E -09
2	90	9.0126712	0.0001321	0.0001981	4.6722 E -11
3	0	138.81118	0.0001321	0.0000660	7.9876 E -11
					1.9163 E -09
					X 2
					$D_{11} = 3.8326 E -09 \text{ N-m}^2 / \text{m}$

RESULTS

The strain at some point of the beam can be expressed as follows²:

$$e_1 = zk \quad (17)$$

If $e_1 = e_{tv} \quad (18)$

$$z = t/2 \quad (\text{for strain due to bending at center of laminate}) \quad (19)$$

then $e_{tv} = M(t/2)/D_{11} \quad (20)$

This is the ply strain in a symmetric laminate due to transverse loading. However, this must be added to the ply strain from the axial compression or axial tension external load condition to calculate the total strain due to combined axial and transverse loading:

$$e_{\text{design}} = e_{c,t} \pm e_{tv} \quad (21)$$

where

$$e_{c,t} = R_{\text{bps}} e_{\text{mSF}\Delta T} \quad (22)$$

R_{bps} = buckled panel strain ratio

$e_{\text{mSF}\Delta T}$ = f(maximum strain, Safety Factor, thermal strain)

The buckled panel strain ratio is empirically developed and is a function of panel rigidity, stiffener rigidity, and structural load:

$$R_{\text{bps}} = f[\%(EI)_{\text{panel}}, \%(EI)_{\text{stiffener}}, \text{structural load \%}] \quad (23)$$

As used in aerospace design, Margin of Safety (MS) is the percentage by which the ultimate strength of a member exceeds the design load. The design load is the applied load, or maximum probable load, multiplied by a specified factor of safety:

$$MS = \frac{e_{cu,tu}}{e_{\text{design}}} - 1 = \frac{\pm xxx \mid (ult)}{\text{(combined axial \& transverse loading)}} \quad (24)$$

REFERENCES:

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